

Massive outbreak of *Metopoplax ditomoides* (Hemiptera, Oxycarenidae) in Doñana National Park (Huelva, Andalucía, Spain)

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Abstract. The first massive outbreak of *Metopoplax ditomoides* in a natural habitat, observed in March 2025 in Doñana National Park (Spain), was reported. Thousands of individuals aggregated on vehicles and nearby structures, a phenomenon previously known only from winter aggregations in urban or agricultural settings. The event likely resulted from unusual climatic conditions, possibly combined with potential visual or chemical cues. Future monitoring is needed to determine whether this was an exceptional episode or part of a recurrent trend under climate change.

Key words: Heteroptera, Oxycarenidae, *Metopoplax ditomoides*, massive outbreak, Doñana National Park, Spain.

Introduction

Insect outbreaks have been known to humans since biblical times (Exodus). The phenomenon occurs in many regions worldwide and has been intensively studied in certain groups, such as locusts and grasshoppers, due to their significant impact on human life, particularly in arid and impoverished areas of Africa (Uvarov 1977). Two books (Barbosa & Schultz 1987; Barbosa et al. 2012), cover several topics related to insect outbreaks.

In the order Hemiptera, the most notable mass outbreaks are the synchronised emergences of periodical cicadas (*Magicicada* spp.) (Williams & Simon 1995). This phenomenon has been widely covered by the media, including newspapers, television, social media, and online platforms. The sunn pest (*Eurygaster* spp.) and the wheat stink bug (*Aelia* spp.) are significant cereal pests, especially of wheat and barley. Substantial outbreaks of these species have been reported in many European, North African, and Asian countries (Güllü et al. 2024). Massive outbreaks have been reported in, at least, ten different families of Heteroptera belonging to three infraorders, Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomidae (Mathew & Sudheendrakumar 1992; Tanaka 2014; Thakur 2024; Yathom 1980), Scutelleridae (Javahery et al. 2000); Coreidae (Dimkpa et al. 2019; Markova et al. 2021), Cydnidae (Lo Verde & Carapezza 2018), Lygaeidae (Lanham 1975; Maistrelloa et al. 2006; Al Antary et al. 2019; Scaccini & Furlan 2019), Oxycarenidae (Nakache & Klein 1992; Wermelinger et al. 2005), Rhyparochromidae (González et al. 2022); Cimicomorpha: Miridae, (Kobayasi et al. 2011; Šedivý & Řehák 2000; Ramegowda et al. 2022), Tingidae (Neimorovets

et al. 2017; Rothschild, 1968) and Leptopodomorpha: Leptopodidae (Günther 2004).

Very few of these outbreaks have been observed in natural habitats. Most occur in agricultural systems (Schaefer & Panizzi 2000), some in urban areas, and many are associated with invasive species.

In the family Oxycarenidae, apart from the cases observed in *Oxycarenus lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787) and *O. hyalinipennis* (A. Costa, 1847), there are two other species that have also been involved in documented mass outbreaks: *Leptodemus minutus* (Jakovlev, 1876) and *Metopoplax ditomoides* (A. Costa, 1843) (Zanon 1921, 1922; Baena & Moro 2025).

Metopoplax ditomoides is known to form winter aggregations in houses, farms and buildings in cultivated or suburban areas (Baena & Moro 2025). In all these places, the behaviour of *M. ditomoides* follows a common pattern: adults of the new generation enter building cavities inaccessible to humans, passing through cracks, grooves and holes, where they rest to estivate and hibernate. The owners of the buildings are unaware of these aggregations. When temperature differences between the inside and outside of buildings are high, the insects move indoors, emerging into rooms through any available passageways connecting their hibernation sites. If the buildings are not visited during the winter, the individuals accumulate in the rooms and are found dead in large numbers when the owners open the buildings. Massive outbreaks of the species in natural areas were previously unknown, as one was observed in Doñana National Park. This paper documents a massive outbreak of *M. ditomoides* in Doñana National Park (Spain).

Observations**

The phenomenon occurred on March 29, 2025, beginning around 2:00 p.m. (local time), when thousands of flying individuals began landing on and inside several SUVs and vans parked at the access control point to Doñana National Park (37.0227871, -6.5549339). The roofs, hoods and windows of the vehicles were covered with thousands of *M. ditomoides* (Fig. 1). Many individuals that had fallen from the vehicles were also observed on the ground beneath the SUVs. The massive aggregation of insects continued until around 5:00 p.m. By that time, most specimens were on the ground, while others were flying in groups away from the aggregation point. No mating behaviour was observed.

Fig. 1. Aggregation of *Metopoplax ditomoides* on SUVs parked at the access control point of the Doñana Biological Reserve (a), and *M. ditomoides* in lateral view (top), ventral view (bottom left), and dorsal view (bottom right) (b).

At the outbreak site, the scrubland belongs to a unit known as “monte blanco”, so named for the predominantly white colour of its sandy soil. The vegetation corresponds to a xeric community mainly composed of *Cistus halimifolius* and *Stauracanthus genistoides*. These two species are accompanied by several species of Cistaceae, such as *Cistus calycinus* and *Cistus libanotis*,

and by Lamiaceae, including *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Lavandula pedunculata* subsp. *pedunculata* and *Thymus mastichina*.

Two or three days later, the phenomenon recurred, but with fewer individuals. On that occasion, the insects entered the access control building, forcing the guard to leave the premises.

Specimens were collected and identified in the laboratory using the keys provided by Péricart (1999).

Discussion

The causes of this striking phenomenon remain unknown. It occurred unexpectedly, and detailed observations were not possible. However, several factors may have contributed to the mass emergence of *M. ditomoides*. In March 2025, Doñana National Park was colder and rainier than in previous years, and the 29th was the first sunny day, with an average temperature (16.3 °C) higher than any previous day that month. It was also the first day in March when the maximum temperature reached 25 °C (Fig. 2). This warming may have triggered the emergence of hibernating Oxycarenidae from their winter refuges.

Fig. 2. Air temperature dynamics in Doñana during early spring 2025. (a) Daily evolution of mean (Mean), maximum (Max), and minimum (Min) air temperatures over the first nine days of April. (b) Hourly temperature fluctuations recorded every five minutes over three consecutive days (28-30 March). Colours and line types have been selected for accessibility for colour-blind readers.

The concentration of white vehicles parked at the control point may have been another contributing factor to the aggregation, possibly due to the emission or reflection of certain types of radiation – thermal, polarised, or ultraviolet – or perhaps even due to chemical cues such as fuel residues or exhaust gases.

Finally, the presence of traces of aggregation pheromone on overwintering individuals – or even active pheromone emission by *M. ditomoides* adults –

might have reinforced or amplified the response to the other stimuli.

In future years, it will be important to monitor this phenomenon closely to determine whether it was an exceptional event linked to an unusually cold and wet season or could recur in the context of climate change.

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** Just as this article was being laid out and was ready for publication, one of the authors (JMVC) observed a new mass occurrence, which is briefly described below:

On 19 May 2026 at 4:06 p.m. (local time), at Choza de Huerta Tejada (Aznaicázar, Seville, Spain; 37.071340, – 6.281615), one of the authors and a colleague were largely covered by thousands of individuals of *M. ditomoides* immediately after exiting a vehicle while exchanging field equipment. This observation closely resembles the massive aggregation event described in the present study. Notably, it coincided with the highest temperature ($\approx 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) recorded during May 2026 at this locality (Fig. 3), following a period of milder conditions. We believe this additional record reinforces the hypothesis that sudden increases in temperature after cooler periods may trigger synchronized emergence and aggregation behaviour in this species.

Fig. 3. Temperature and relative humidity during May at the locality Choza de Huerta Tejada. In blue, relative humidity; in red, temperature, max.= maximum, min.= minimum. Graphic modified for Meteoblue.